

FDI and Import-Export Activities in Vietnam

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to review the research on the impact of FDI on import and export activities. On that basis, we conduct an analysis of the current situation of import and export activities in Vietnam and make recommendations to improve the efficiency of import and export activities in Vietnam.

Keywords: FDI, import and export, Vietnam.

1. Introduction

According to many economic organizations, Vietnam, along with Malaysia and India, are the top three countries on the list of supposedly benefiting from US-China trade tensions, however, the extent of Vietnam's benefits Male so far is not much. The total import-export value of the whole country in the first 7 months of 2019 was only about US \$ 288.47 billion, up 7.9% compared to the same period in 2018.

According to a report of the General Department of Customs, in the first 7 months of 2019, crude oil exports reached about 2,494 thousand tons (about US \$ 1,285 million), up 8.7% in volume and down 0.2% in value compared to with the same period in 2018. Meanwhile, the export turnover of wood and wood products reached about US \$ 5.67 billion, up 16.4% over the same period in 2018. Textiles and garments reached US \$ 18.34 billion, increased by 10.5% over the same period in 2018. Regarding footwear, the total export turnover reached US \$ 10.44 billion, up 13.8% over the same period in 2018. Computers, electronic products and components also saw an impressive increase in the past 7 months. Accordingly, the total export value of this commodity group in the first 7 months of 2019 to nearly 18.62 billion USD, up 14.9% over the same period in 2018.

Regarding the import of goods, the General Department of Customs' statistics showed that the complete units of automobiles increased sharply in the first 7 months. Specifically, by the end of July 2019, import of complete units of automobiles reached 88 thousand units, worth US \$ 1.94 billion, up 365.6% in volume and 319.4% in value compared to with the same period of 2018; The volume of imported petroleum reached about 5.14 million tons, worth about US \$ 3.15 billion, down 34.8% in volume and down 39.8% in value compared to the same period in 2018. Chemical products substance reached US \$ 3.03 billion, up 7% over the same period in 2018. Meanwhile, imports of fabrics reached US \$ 7.76 billion, up 4.6% over the same period in 2018. For machinery , equipment, tools and spare parts, by the end of July 2019, the country reached US \$ 20.85 billion, up 12.7% over the same period in 2018. Imports of computers, electrical products electronic devices and components reached US \$ 28.2 billion, an increase of 19% compared to the first 7 months of 2018. Mobile phones and components by the end of July 2019, the import of phones and components of the whole country reached 7.06 billion USD, down 4.4% compared to the same period in 2018.

2. Literature review

2.1. The impact of FDI on exports in the host country

Researchers in many countries around the world have clarified the impact of FDI on exports in the recipient country with empirical studies in many different countries. Studies have shown that FDI has an impact on exports in the recipient country through a direct effect channel and a series of impact transmission channels such as competitive pressure channel, technology transfer channel, and labor migration and knowledge transfer, link channels between FDI enterprises and domestic enterprises ... Through which, the export of goods of the receiving countries increased due to: (i) exports of FDI enterprises themselves. in the host country; (ii) the

ability of domestic firms to export increases due to the positive spillover effects of FDI (Aitken & Hansen & Harrison, 1997; Blomstrom & Kokko, 2003; Bwalya, 2006; Gorg & Greenaway, 2004; Greenaway & Kneller, 2004; Günther Jutta, 2002; Kneller & Pisu, 2007; Nakamura, 2002; Sun, 2009; Wagner, 2007; Wang & Blomstrom, 1992).

FDI enterprises with advantages in capital, technology, business organization and management know-how have exerted considerable pressure to force domestic exporters to change their management methods and improve their capacity. technology, managerial level and quality of human resources to improve their competitiveness. Under the increase of competition and to resist competition, domestic exporters are forced to operate more efficiently, innovate and apply new technologies earlier, so their export capacity and value domestic enterprises increase and resonate to increase the export value of receiving countries (Blomstrom & Kokko, 1998; Kokko & Tansini & Zejan, 1996; Kokko et al., 2001; Wang & Blomstrom, 1992).

A study by Aitken et al. (1997) in Mexico during 1986-1990 found a positive impact of MNCs on the ability of domestic firms to participate in export markets. Similarly, Greenaway et al. (2004) analyzed the case of England in 1992-1996 and observed the positive impact of MNCs in improving competitiveness and increasing export capacity of domestic enterprises. geography. The results confirm that domestic enterprises are learned by R&D activities of MNCs and the operation process of MNCs increases competitiveness and forces domestic enterprises to increase labor productivity to survive. As a result, domestic enterprises improve their production capacity, increase the scale and export value. In a empirical study in the UK in the period of 1998-2002, Greenaway & Kneller (2008) showed that the presence of FDI enterprises in the UK has created new export enterprises in the country, creating more much competitive pressure and had a positive impact on British exports.

FDI enterprises also bring advanced production technology, skills, management skills, etc. that domestic enterprises can receive through technology transfer. The association of production and business between domestic enterprises and FDI enterprises contributes to the increase in export of these enterprises due to learning in the process of linking with FDI enterprises. At the same time, workers in these enterprises are also trained in skills to produce and export goods that meet the standards of FDI enterprises (CIEM, 2011).

Kokko (1994) affirmed that the ability of domestic enterprises to absorb technology and technology level are factors that influence the appearance of positive spillover effects of FDI on exports of domestic enterprises. Hamida (2011) also confirms this and is made clear by empirical studies in various disciplines. Research has shown that, in the manufacturing industry, domestic enterprises with high technology level get more benefits from the spillover effects of FDI thanks to the increased competition compared to domestic enterprises. medium and low technology level.

Kaufmann (1997), Fosfuri et al (2001) and Glass & Saggi (2002) have also shown that domestic enterprises can access and receive knowledge transfer from FDI enterprises due to the labor movement from FDI sector to domestic economic sector. This effect appears when workers trained to work in FDI enterprises move to work for domestic enterprises or establish new businesses themselves. These workers will apply the knowledge and experience in producing export goods learned in FDI enterprises to the production of export goods in domestic enterprises, thereby improving opportunities and capabilities. export goods to these enterprises (Hamida & Gugler, 2009; Todo et al., 2009).

FDI is often classified by investment type, including vertical FDI and horizontal FDI (Fukao & Amano, 1998). In vertical FDI, the motivation for conducting FDI is to seek the supply of input materials necessary for the final goods production processes of the investors. In contrast, the form of horizontal FDI is the construction of similar factories, goods production and service provision in the host country. Clare (1996) points out that FDI inflows can positively impact the export activities of domestic firms in industries that produce raw materials (upstream industry) and processed raw materials (downstream). industry) belongs to the same value chain (both upstream and downstream) through vertical links. Meanwhile, Kokko et al. (2001) and Alvarez & Lopez (2008)

pointed out the positive impact of FDI on exports of domestic enterprises through horizontal linkages, and affirmed that FDI has an effect. Actively promoting export activities of domestic enterprises operating in the same field.

However, there are also studies proving that FDI does not have an impact or negative impact on the export of the recipient country such as the study of Barrios et al. (2003) for the case of Spain, the study of Aitken & Harrison (1999) for the case of Venezuela, the study of Djankov & Hoekman (2000) for the case of the Czech Republic, the study of Bernard & Jensen (2004) for the case of the United States. In the study of spillover effects of FDI on Spain's export activities in 1990-1998, Barrios et al. (2003) found no evidence to prove that FDI has a positive spillover effect on exports. export activities of domestic Spanish enterprises in this period. Bernard & Jensen (2004) also point out that FDI has no spillover effect on exports of US manufacturing firms. This is also the conclusion of several other studies of Lutz et al. (2003) and Greenaway et al (2004).

Thus, the results of the research on the effects of the "export spillover effect" have shown many different and inconsistent results. These impacts depend heavily on the type of FDI and the differences in business strategies between domestic firms and MNCs (Kneller & Pisu, 2007). On the other hand, studies on spillover effects of FDI focus mainly on analysis within a country, usually the country attracts only a certain type of FDI with many different potential spillover effects. For this reason, an analysis of the effects of spillover effects is often from a less comprehensive perspective and lacks widespread applicability to other countries (Javorcik & Spatareanu, 2008).

Nguyen Thanh Xuan & Yuqing Xing (2008) pointed out that FDI has a positive impact on Vietnam's exports. Accordingly, the average if a country's FDI to Vietnam increased by 1% will increase Vietnam's exports to that country by 0.13%. The study also pointed out that the weak dong holdings were one of the important causes promoting Vietnam's export growth in the period 1990-2004. Through a series of tests, the study shows that the impact of the free trade agreement (FTA) between Vietnam and some countries on exports also has a clear difference. While the FTA with the US strongly promotes Vietnam's exports to this market, it is not enough to conclude the FTA with the ASEAN countries to boost Vietnam's exports to the bloc countries. Although the study mentioned free trade agreements when assessing the impact of FDI on Vietnam's exports, the study only analyzed the impact of FDI on Vietnam's exports. in the period 1990-2004. Therefore, the study has not assessed the impact of FDI on the entire foreign trade of Vietnam (including exports, imports and trade balance) and has not yet shown the effects of Vietnam's WTO accession to access to FDI and its impact on import, export and trade balance in Vietnam.

Studying from the perspective of "export spillover effects" of FDI, Sajid Anwar & Nguyen Phi Lan (2011) apply theories of international business to verify the existence of foreign corporations that can be beneficial. for domestic enterprises through inter-firm linkages. Using Heckman's two-step estimation model, the study showed that FDI enterprises' activities have a clear positive effect on (1) export behavior of domestic enterprises, (2) the benefits profits from the export of domestic enterprises. In other words, the spillover effect of FDI on Vietnam's exports is mainly on horizontal FDI and the goods supply services sector. The study also showed that horizontal FDI has a positive, significant effect on exports of all domestic enterprises while the supply of goods affects only businesses with limited scientific level. Export effect will be stronger if foreign enterprises invest is an export-oriented enterprise. Specifically, these businesses create a competitive environment that makes domestic enterprises always have to mobilize, from which the volume of goods produced and exported also increases. The results suggest that other factors that should be considered in this relationship are: (i) technological capacity of domestic enterprises, (ii) structure of domestic enterprises, (iii) strategy of domestic enterprises, (iv) geographical factors of foreign enterprises. New in this study is the business management perspective, focusing on the activities of enterprises. However, the lack of data availability and the use of cross-array data is a limitation of the study, which can lead to undesirable biases in the results of the study. The research only stops at making tests on the spillover effects of FDI on domestic enterprises without specifying the impact channel and conditions to create spillover effects from FDI to exports.

of these businesses. In addition, the study only considers the effect of FDI on exports without considering this impact on Vietnam's imports and net exports.

Using the econometric model, Nguyen Bich Ngoc (2016) has shown that FDI has a positive spillover effect on exports of Vietnam's manufacturing and processing industry. The study shows that the spillover effect of FDI on exports of this industry is indirect effects through impact transmission channels rather than direct impacts. The strength of the study is the application of the econometric model, drawing conclusive conclusions on the spillover effects from FDI to exports of manufacturing and processing industry in Vietnam. However, the study also assesses the impact of FDI on exports of an industry but has not assessed the impact of FDI on Vietnam's overall import and export activities.

The typical studies in Vietnam have indicated an additional link between FDI inflows and exports. This is also consistent with the results of international studies, when FDI inflows in Vietnam tend to take advantage of cheap human resources as well as a series of preferential policies of the State to seek profits. A clear difference in technology capacity, production capacity and quality of human resources can also make Vietnam an export country for MNCs to invest and conduct production, and export to other countries (like the case of China).

The impact of FDI on export goods structure

It can be said that not many studies in the world have clearly analyzed the impact of FDI on the export goods structure of the host country. There has not been a separate study on the impact of FDI on the structure of imported goods, but FDI analysis is only one of the factors affecting the restructuring of export goods in the host country.

Hoekman & Djankov (1997) studied the determinants of the structure of exports in countries of Central and Eastern Europe. Research and analyze the factors that affect changes in the structure of export goods and focus on the structure of export goods of Central and Eastern Europe in the period 1990- 1995. Factors considered including imports of intermediate inputs, FDI, and subcontracting. FDI is one of the independent variables of the model which emphasizes the form of joint venture of FDI. The test results do not show the important role of FDI in the change of export structure of this region except Finland. The reason is explained by the fact that FDI inflows into Central and Eastern Europe are typically focused on services and distribution, while this study is looking at the impact of FDI on migration, restructuring export goods.

A study by Bin Xu & Jiangyong Lu (2006) on the impact of FDI on the quality of Chinese exports is conducted during 1998-2005. The study uses the independent variables as the proportion of FDI in GDP, real GDP per capita, output proportion of new products (R&D), the average wage rate and the proportion of output output of FDI enterprises. The conclusion is that FDI enterprises and other enterprises with a lower level of ownership are decisive factors for the quality of the structure of export goods of China. However, the role of FDI in changing the structure of export goods in terms of quantity has not been mentioned and the change in quality is not clear.

Zhang & Liu (2008) pointed out that FDI has an impact on the export goods structure of Korea and China in the direction of promoting the export of products with high processing and technology content. However, the author only concludes that FDI has an impact on export structure of Korea and China without clarifying the impact of FDI on changes in export structure of these two countries.

Bin Xu & Jiangyong Lu (2009) also studied the impact of FDI, processing trade on the structure of exports and the changes in the structure of exports. The strength of this study is that the authors have considered the impact of FDI on the quality of export goods structure to answer the question why China has seen a sharp increase in quality in goods structure, export compared to the world in the 2000-2005 period. The conclusion of the study is that both FDI and processing trade are important for improving the quality of China's export goods structure.

2.2. The impact of FDI on imports in the host country

In general, the impact of FDI on imports in the host country does not receive as much attention from researchers as it does on exports. Most studies show that at the early stage of investment (in the short term), FDI increases imports, whereas in the long term, FDI can reduce the import of the recipient country.

Research by Penelope Pacheco (2005) has shown that as soon as MNCs are established in the host country, they will import certain types of inputs (usually basic components and intermediate goods produced). originated from the head office in the country of investment) to meet the quality standards required by the international market. Therefore, FDI inflows increase the import demand. Chani et al. (2014) also affirmed that FDI can increase the import of production inputs because most of the production inputs of the service industry are related to high technology that the recipient countries have not yet produced. exports, must depend greatly on imports. Therefore, FDI inflows from countries supplying inputs to receiving countries are often more attractive and focused on attracting.

According to Yasir Khan et al (2018), there exists a positive relationship between FDI and imports in the host country in the short term. That is, in the short term FDI will increase imports in the host country and vice versa. Jayakumar et al. (2014) also stated that, at the initial investment stage, FDI enterprises tend to import equipment, machinery, installation equipment and experts who are not available or do not meet the standard. Standards of FDI enterprises in host countries. This makes imports in the host country increase. Studies by Tabassum et al. (2012), Muhammad et al. (2014) also show that FDI increases foreign imports into the host country.

Formally, FDI is often divided into vertical FDI and horizontal FDI (Fukao & Amano, 1998). According to Franco et al. (2010), the impact of FDI on imports in the host country, according to this approach, is highly dependent on the form of investment. Horizontal FDI will increase the import of raw materials and materials from investing countries to receiving countries. Meanwhile, Inui & Seki (1997) point out that horizontal FDI has two trends: (i) increasing imports of intermediate goods for production and (ii) increasing exports of goods. finally from countries receiving investment due to relocation of production sites.

A more detailed division of Eiteman et al. (1995), the motives of enterprises when conducting foreign direct investment include: (1) FDI seeking markets, (2) FDI seeking sources raw materials, (3) FDI seeks production efficiency,

(4) FDI seeks human capital advantages and (5) FDI seeks political security. In particular, FDI seeks for raw materials, FDI seeks political security and FDI seeks human resources that have a positive positive impact on exports, while FDI seeks markets and FDI seeks. It is also important to find out production efficiency at a very positive positive effect on the import of the recipient country, even causing these countries to fall into a trade deficit.

Some studies show that the impact of FDI on the import of the recipient country depends on many factors. Dunning (1979) introduced an OLI model to explain the investment behavior of countries and MNCs. Accordingly, a country will receive FDI, invest in FDI, domestic production for export or import depends on the owner advantages, location advantages and localization advantages of the country. yourself with the country you intend to invest in. Specifically, if a country does not have a lot of ownership advantages, location advantages or internalization advantages, then it may be appropriate to consider importing goods. , machinery to meet domestic demand. Developing this theory, Liu et al. (2001) point out that most MNCs are established in developed countries. These companies gradually open their subsidiaries in less developed countries to take advantage of their comparative advantages such as labor and cheap resources. Therefore, FDI and the importation exist at the same time and have the effect of promoting each other. Aizenman & Noy (2006) add the factors of market openness and the strength of financial markets, which influence the impact of FDI on imports of receiving countries.

Pfafermayr (1996) uses data collected from FDI enterprises to indicate that FDI has an additional effect, promoting imports. Fukakaku & Mello (2000) add that these effects tend to be stronger when FDI inflows are invested in South Asian countries compared to countries of the same level of development in Latin America. Studies by Do & Levchenko (2004), Lane & Ferretti (2004), Rose & Spiegel (2004) and Swenson (2004) also show that the increase in FDI inflows not only promotes international trade but also increasing the total factor productivity (TFP) of the host country. This spillover effect of FDI will increase labor productivity, make goods produce more and consequently become more active in international trade (Driffield & Love, 2007).

Various studies of the model, the time and the scope of the study also provide some conflicting conclusions. A study by Belderbos & Sleuwaegen (1998) points to the inverse relationship between FDI and imports of some industries and concludes that these two activities hold back each other. Supplementing the above view, when studying a number of industries in 13 developing countries, Svensson (1998) has demonstrated that FDI in the goods-producing industries ultimately has a negative effect on imports, while FDI into intermediate goods creation industries. FDI into the goods-creating industries ultimately reduces the importing countries' imports as imported goods are replaced by the final goods produced by the FDI enterprises themselves. When studying the impact of FDI on Indonesia's import and export activities, Muhammad Albahi (2016) also pointed out that FDI has a positive impact on imports, reducing the import of the recipient country in the long term. The study also pointed out that Indonesia's imports are also influenced by other factors such as economic growth, conditions of the international economy, exchange rates, etc.

Empirical research on the relationship between FDI and import-export in Vietnam has not been conducted much. Most studies only assess the impact of FDI on exports, while import is also an important economic activity, greatly affecting the trade balance of Vietnam. proper mind.

Up to now, there is only one empirical study on the relationship of FDI and imports and the trade balance in Vietnam, that is the study of Sajid Anwar & Nguyen Phi Lan (2011). The study examined the relationship between: (i) FDI with exports; (ii) FDI with imports; (iii) FDI with net exports of Vietnam with 19 largest trading partners in 1990-2007. This study is divided into three phases: (1) before the Asian financial crisis (1990-1997), (2) during the Asian financial crisis (1998-2000), (3) after the financial crisis (2001-2007). Using the gravity model, the authors point out the complementary relationship between FDI and import and export: FDI into Vietnam promotes both exports and imports. On the contrary, both exports and imports promote FDI attraction. The impact of FDI on net exports is positive in the post-financial crisis period but is not clear in the previous two periods. The division of this research phase into three smaller stages is very correct and helps to appreciate the relationship between FDI and import-export in Vietnam. On the other hand, research results on the negative impact of geographical conditions in the trade balance and the positive impact of middle income on exports and imports are a new feature in the study.

In general, so far there has been no research on the impact of FDI on import-export activities in Vietnam on all three aspects: (i) the impact of FDI on import-export turnover; (ii) the impact of FDI on the structure of import and export goods; (iii) The impact of FDI on the import and export market. The studies only focus on studying the impact of FDI on exports or export activities of a specific industry in Vietnam.

Impact of FDI on imported goods structure

Studies by Penelope Pacheco (2005), Jayakumar et al (2014), Chani et al (2014), Khan et al (2018), Tabassum et al (2012) have shown that FDI has a direct impact. to change the structure of import countries of the recipient countries in the direction of increasing the proportion of production means through the channel of importing machinery, equipment and production inputs of FDI enterprises. This fact occurs in most countries receiving investment in the early stages, especially in developing countries. Most of FDI enterprises have to import machinery, equipment, input materials produced from the outside because the domestic can not meet. This changes the export structure of the recipient country. In addition, if FDI enterprises have to import necessary technologies (because they cannot be produced domestically), this also makes the proportion of production

materials group in the structure of imported goods of the receiving countries. The number of investment recipients increases (Muhammad Albahi, 2016; Muhammad et al., 2014; Selma, 2013).

In addition, Penelope Pacheco (2005), Jayakumar et al. (2014) also assert that when FDI enterprises are involved, instead of importing, these countries will consume goods produced in the country. by the FDI enterprises themselves. Thus, FDI has a direct impact on the structure of imports, changing the structure of imports of the host country towards reducing the proportion of consumer goods through the channel of replacing imported goods with manufactured goods. exported by FDI enterprises in the host country.

Impact on the scope and structure of import and export markets

A WTO study (1996) on trade and FDI has shown that most of the host countries have become trade partners of the host country due to input and output constraints of the production process. and product consumption. In addition, investors will take advantage of the investment destination to produce goods and export back to the country due to the expensive domestic production costs. Therefore, the more foreign investors make a foreign direct investment in a country, the greater the scope of its import-export market will expand. Besides, according to Lionel Fontagné (1999), through the extensive distribution network of MNCs around the world, goods of recipient countries can penetrate more easily into the markets of countries. in the world, including the fastidious markets, demanding strict quality of goods such as the US market, Japan, the EU ...

Aitken et al. (1997) also pointed out that FDI enterprises are often present in many countries and operate under the distribution network of MNCs. Therefore, FDI enterprises will be the best and fastest suppliers of information about export markets in foreign countries, about foreign customers, about goods distribution channels in foreign markets ... Through linking production and business with FDI enterprises, domestic exporters will have the opportunity to obtain information about the export market and from that, they can have access to export markets.

Impacts on import-export market structure: The impact of FDI on changing the import-export market structure of the host country has hardly received the attention of researchers both in the world and in Vietnam. Male. The topic is expected to clarify this impact in Vietnam.

3. The impact of the US-China trade war on import and export of Vietnamese goods

Evaluating in detail the overall impacts from the US-China trade war to Vietnam's import and export of goods, the Central Institute for Economic Management said that Vietnam is a beneficiary country according to relative meaning and there are some significant opportunities in this trade war. However, these assessments are limited to the tariff measures used by the US and China.

The tariff barriers that the United States and China add to each other are invisible, increasing export opportunities for third countries, including Vietnam. Increasing uncertainty in the context of a trade war may also cause large multinational companies around the world to transfer part or all of their manufacturing facilities in China to other countries, such as Vietnam.

However, in the opposite direction, Vietnam also faces many risks and disadvantages. Due to difficulties in output, Chinese goods may be pushed to Vietnam market and compete with Vietnamese products in other third markets. Despite being a beneficiary country, Vietnam also faces many disadvantages, that is being monitored by the United States and China, and even taking actions and policies affecting Vietnam's exports to these countries. The risk will be greater if Vietnam fails to maintain dialogue, share information and experiences with

other major economies (such as Japan, the European Union, Australia ...) on assessments and forecasts. and policy of dealing with US-China trade war.

US-China trade tensions continue to escalate following President Donald Trump's Twitter statement on August 1, 2019, that the US will apply the remaining 10% tariff on the remaining \$ 300 billion on imported goods. From China on September 1, 2019 and the tax rate may increase to 25% later. The imposition of this tax has been warned by the US if China delayed or failed to fulfill its commitments to increase US imports. Thus, it can be said that if this tax is implemented, almost all goods imported from China (about US \$ 550 billion) are imposed by the US from 10% to 25%.

In the context of increasing US-China trade tensions, experts recommend that Vietnam should proactively develop and update scenarios to cope with the developments of the US-China trade war. At the same time, reviewing the policy regulations, ensuring that there are appropriate tools and policy space to guide imported goods and respond to adverse changes in the world market. In particular, it is necessary to pay attention to strict control and take measures to eliminate the situation of fraudulent foreign goods of Vietnamese origin for export to the US; Focus solutions to remove barriers to Vietnam's exports to markets, including the Chinese market.

At the same time, it is necessary to improve the statistical information system, to avoid the existence of big differences between data imported from China (published by Vietnam) and data exported to Vietnam (published by China). Father); Continue to reform the business investment environment in a fairer, more favorable and competitive manner; Constantly contacting and consolidating the confidence of foreign investors; Complete, specify standards for foreign investors entering Vietnam, in accordance with the socio-economic development priorities. In addition, it is necessary to promote cooperation with countries in the group of powerful countries to share information, assessments and experience in responding to these countries' policies to the complicated developments of the US-China war, and , continue to advocate for free trade and multilateral trading system ...

The Ministry of Industry and Trade said that it will continue to closely monitor the development of the US-China trade war to make specific economic development plans and take proactive measures to boost exports. At the same time, enterprises will be encouraged to export advantageous goods, as well as strictly control the import and export of goods from border gates to avoid frauds of goods origin; On the other hand, it will organize activities to connect enterprises exporting agricultural and aquatic products of Vietnam to enterprises with Chinese import demand through border gates, especially for Vietnamese goods that are beneficial. China and China are in great demand such as fruits, seafood, rice, coffee ...

In addition, the Ministry of Industry and Trade also focuses on the implementation of Vietnam's international integration commitments, ensuring a more efficient and sustainable integration process to enhance the utilization of opportunities brought about by New generation FTA; Strengthening import and export development solutions and measures for each important market; seek the possibility of expanding new potential export markets and at the same time consolidate and expand the market share of Vietnamese goods in traditional markets, markets that are FTA partners.

4. Measures to improve the efficiency of goods import and export in Vietnam

In order to continue promoting export activities, fulfilling the objectives set out in the Commodity Import and Export Strategy for the period of 2011-2020, with orientations to 2030, in the coming time, some following measures should be attached to the following solutions. :

Firstly, continue expanding export markets. Expanding export markets is considered a long-term strategy to help Vietnamese enterprises participate deeply in the regional value chain, improve export production capacity

and compete. At the same time, helping Vietnamese businesses to rub with the outside world, have conditions to develop production and business activities and affirm their new position in the international arena.

Secondly, continue to restructure export products towards increasing the proportion of high value-added products. In particular, for export agricultural products: Change from exporting raw materials to processed products, from simple processed products to processed products with high added value. For industrial exports: Change from low value-added products to high value-added products.

Thirdly, improve the quality of exported products: Accelerate the formulation and application of a system of national standards harmonized with international standards, regional standards and foreign standards for exported goods. Export, including technical standards, food hygiene and safety standards, environmental standards. Building the capacity of testing and certification organizations to meet international standards to serve the assessment of conformity with national standards, international standards, regional standards and water standards. external standards and specific standards for exports.

Fourth, improve efficiency and innovate trade promotion methods, focusing on export-advantageous goods, potential markets and niches to open new markets to diversify. export market. Continue to negotiate, sign and implement bilateral and multilateral trade agreements in the direction of facilitating and improving the competitive advantage of Vietnam's exports on the world market ...

Fifthly, strengthening national branding, export product branding and enterprise branding Building Vietnam's national brand in export markets. In addition, encourage and support enterprises to build export products reaching national brands and branding of enterprises. Completing policies to support businesses in establishing and protecting intellectual property rights of enterprises in the domestic market and in export markets.

Sixthly, strengthening the monitoring, researching of policy developments and impact analysis on Vietnam: In the context of increasing protectionism, especially the rapid and unpredictable developments of trade disputes. between the United States and China, regulators, industry associations, businesses need to strengthen research, update changes in trade policies and regulations of countries, especially in markets. major exports; analyze the impact of these changes on Vietnam's production and exports to make appropriate adjustments and responses.

Promote early warning to take necessary measures to limit damage from trade remedies lawsuits of importing countries. Disseminate, advise and train export-manufacturing enterprises on the application of goods quality standards to foreign markets. Encouraging and supporting enterprises to develop export products with national quality awards and international quality awards ...

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